

Synthesis of Some New 1, 3, 4-Oxa(thia)diazoles and 1,2,4-Triazoles as Potential Fungicides

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Several 2-arylamino-5-(2, 6-dichlorophenyl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles (II), the corresponding thiadiazoles (III) and 4-aryl-5-(2, 6-dichlorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles (IV) have been prepared by the cyclisation of corresponding 4-aryl-1-(2, 6-dichlorobenzoyl) thiosemicarbazides (I). Oxidation of the triazoles (IV) has furnished the corresponding bis-triazolyl disulphides (V). Four of the tested compounds have shown the fungitoxicity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* comparable to that of the Dithane M-45, a commercial fungicide at 1000 ppm and 100 ppm.

MANY agricultural fungicides contain reactive chlorine atoms, and 1,3,4-oxadiazole¹⁻³, 1,3,4-thiadiazole^{4,5} and 1,2,4-triazole⁶⁻⁹ derivatives also possess various useful biological activities. It was, therefore, speculated that the insertion of 2,6-dichlorophenyl moiety into the biologically versatile heterocycles might result in the fungicides of better performance.

The 1,3,4-oxadiazoles(II), corresponding thiadiazoles(III), 1,2,4-triazoles(IV) and the bis-triazolyl disulphides(V) have been prepared according to the Scheme 1. The required 4-aryl-1-(2,6-dichlorobenzoyl) thiosemicarbazides(I) were prepared by treating 2,6-dichlorobenzoylhydrazine with aryl *iso*-thiocyanates in ethanol¹⁰. The compounds were characterised by their elemental analyses and ir spectra.

Sixteen of the title compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. The results obtained have been compared with *Dithane M-45*, a commercial fungicide, which was also tested under similar conditions. Four of these compounds exhibited the antifungal activity almost in the range of the commercial fungicide at concentrations 1000 ppm and 100 ppm. However, the bis-triazolyl disulphides(V) were found to be more active than the corresponding oxadiazoles(II), thiadiazoles(III) and triazoles(IV).

Experimental

The ir spectra (in KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer, model 521, spectrophotometer.

2,6-Dichlorobenzoylhydrazine was prepared by the method of Covello *et al*¹¹.

4-Aryl-1-(2,6-dichlorobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazides (I) were prepared according to the method of Silberg and Cosma¹⁰. The I thus prepared are as follows: R=H, m.p. 183° (Found: N, 12.06; S, 9.39, C₁₄H₁₁Cl₂N₃OS requires N, 12.35; S, 9.41%); R=*p*-Cl, m.p. 166° (Found: N, 11.12; S, 8.21, C₁₄H₁₀Cl₃N₃OS requires N, 11.21; S, 8.54%); R=*p*-OCH₃, m.p. 179° (Found: N, 11.07; S, 8.73, C₁₅H₁₃Cl₂N₃O₂S requires N, 11.35; S, 8.65%); R=*m*-CH₃, m.p. 196° (Found: N, 12.03; S, 8.84, C₁₅H₁₃Cl₂N₃OS requires N, 11.86; S, 9.04%) and R=*p*-CH₃, m.p. 184° (Found: N, 11.55; S, 9.21, C₁₅H₁₃Cl₂N₃OS requires N, 11.86, S, 9.04%). These compounds were recrystallised from ethanol, and their yield ranged from 78-90%.

2-Arylamino-5-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles(II) were prepared following the method of

Scheme 1

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Silberg and Cosma¹⁰, and were recrystallised from ethanol. The oxadiazoles(II) thus prepared are recorded in Table 1A.

2-Arylamino-5-(2, 6-dichlorophenyl)-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles(III)— These were prepared according to the method of Maffii *et al*¹², and were recrystallised from ethanol. The thiadiazoles(III) thus prepared are recorded in Table 1B.

4-Aryl-5-(2, 6-dichlorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles(IV) were prepared¹³ from the thiosemicarbazides (I), and were recrystallised from ethanol. The triazoles(IV) thus prepared are recorded in Table 1C.

Bis[4-aryl-5-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl] disulphides(V) were prepared by the oxidation of 3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles(IV) with bromine. Thus an ethanolic solution of the compound IV (0.02M) was stirred with bromine (0.02M) in ethanol (15 ml.). The disulphide compound at once began to separate, it was filtered, and recrystallised from ethanol. The bis-triazolyl disulphides(V) thus prepared are recorded in Table 1C.

Fungicidal Screening

The antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique¹⁴ against *A. niger* and *A. flavus* at concentrations 1000 ppm, 100 ppm and 10 ppm.

TABLE 1A—2-ARYLAMINO-5-(2, 6-DICHLOROPHENYL)-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLES(II)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	C(%)		H(%)	
					Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
1 ^a	H	78	209	C ₁₄ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O	54.72	54.90	2.80	2.94
2	p-Chloro	80	216	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₃ N ₃ O	43.13	43.44	2.09	2.35
3 ^b	p-Methoxy	75	231	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	53.29	53.57	3.14	3.27
4	m-Methyl	72	225	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O	56.06	56.25	3.16	3.44
5	p-Methyl	76	236	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O	56.88	56.25	3.28	3.44

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in KBr)

	C=N,	C—O—C,	N—H,	Substituted benzene nucleus
a.	1635	1024	3420	1600, 1585, 780, 745
b.	1630	1020	3455	1600, 1580, 850, 800

TABLE 1B—2-ARYLAMINO-5-(2, 6-DICHLOROPHENYL)-1, 3, 4-THIADIAZOLES(III)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	N%		S%	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
6	H	70	233	C ₁₄ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.87	13.04	9.79	9.94
7 ^a	p-Chloro	75	225	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₃ N ₃ S	11.89	11.78	8.91	8.98
8	p-Methoxy	72	209	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS	11.81	11.93	8.87	9.09
9 ^b	m-Methyl	68	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.19	12.50	9.36	9.52
10	p-Methyl	75	193	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.61	12.50	9.62	9.52

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in KBr)

	C=N,	C—S—C,	N—H,	Substituted benzene nucleus
a.	1625	715	3380	1595, 1575, 850, 775
b.	1632	710	3410	1602, 1580, 800, 780

TABLE 1C—4-ARYL-5-(2, 6-DICHLOROPHENYL)-3-MERCAPTO-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLES (IV) AND THEIR DISULPHIDES(V)

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	N(%)		S(%)	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
4-ARYL-5-(2,6-DICHLOROPHENYL)-3-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES(IV)								
11	H	82	208	C ₁₄ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.91	13.04	9.75	9.94
12 ^a	p-Chloro	84	233	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₃ N ₃ S	11.53	11.78	8.84	8.98
13	p-Methoxy	80	241	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS	11.89	11.93	8.86	9.09
14	m-Methyl	78	239	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.67	12.50	9.70	9.52
15 ^b	p-Methyl	85	246	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	12.36	12.50	9.39	9.52
BIS[4-ARYL-5-(2, 6-DICHLOROPHENYL)-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOL-3-YL] DISULPHIDES(V)								
16 ^c	H	68	181	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ Cl ₄ N ₆ S ₂	13.16	13.08	9.83	9.97
17	p-Chloro	70	204	C ₂₈ H ₁₄ Cl ₆ N ₆ S ₂	11.59	11.81	8.85	9.00
18	p-Methoxy	65	198	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	11.73	11.97	8.06	9.12
19 ^d	m-Methyl	62	200	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ S ₂	12.74	12.54	9.41	9.55
20	p-Methyl	66	207	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ Cl ₄ N ₆ S ₂	12.42	12.54	9.36	9.55

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in ir spectra (in KBr)

	C=N,	S—H,	Substituted benzene nucleus
a.	1615	2580	1600, 1580, 845, 780
b.	1620	2600	1602, 1585, 800, 775
c.	1622	—	1600, 1580, 790, 760
d.	1630	—	1600, 1578, 815, 765

The number of replications in each case was three. The percentage inhibitions by various compounds are recorded in Table 2.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hours.

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hours.

Results and Discussion

All the tested compounds exhibited significant fungitoxicity at 1000 ppm but their toxicity decreased markedly on dilution except in case of the compound No. 17-20 which are the representatives of bis-triazolyl disulphides(V), and inhibited the growth of both the fungal species >50% even at 10 ppm. The fungitoxicity of the compounds varied with fungal species as well, but no generalisation could be made in this regard (Table 2).

thiram (Fig. 2), a common fungicide, where it has been suggested^{1,5} that it reacts with thiols, the important cellular constituents, and the mechanism of the reaction involves S—S bond fission.

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TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound serial as in Tables 1A, 1B & 1C	AVERAGE PERCENTAGE INHIBITION AFTER 96 HOURS					
	Organism— <i>A. niger</i>			Organism— <i>A. flavus</i>		
	Concentrations used			Concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
2	87.1	61.6	32.4	91.3	55.1	25.8
3	100	62.7	31.8	95.0	52.8	30.1
4	82.9	59.4	32.3	86.8	50.3	21.3
5	86.3	60.5	31.7	92.5	49.2	23.2
7	85.4	60.4	30.6	89.6	53.2	25.1
8	100	61.3	29.7	92.3	52.1	28.3
9	82.6	58.2	29.8	86.4	49.6	19.2
10	85.7	58.9	29.6	90.2	49.9	21.7
12	90.2	68.8	40.4	83.6	63.2	47.4
13	85.4	62.1	41.2	91.1	53.4	41.2
14	82.8	64.5	39.3	80.4	62.8	39.5
15	88.7	59.3	43.0	88.5	54.7	38.4
17	100	84.6	53.7	98.5	78.8	51.3
18	98.8	85.0	54.1	100	79.2	50.4
19	100	83.9	50.6	96.4	80.3	51.5
20	100	83.8	52.4	99.3	79.0	52.7
<i>Dithane M-45</i> (A commercial fungicide)	100	85.2	72.4	95.7	81.2	66.2

These results show that the oxadiazoles (II, Compound Nos. 2-5) were relatively more fungitoxic than their thiadiazole analogues (III, Compound Nos. 7-10) but the difference in their fungicidal action was of very low order. In general, the bis-triazolyl disulphides (V, Compound Nos. 17-20) were more potent than the parent triazoles (IV, Compound Nos. 12-15), and the level of their fungitoxicity was also very high. This could be expected from their structures (Fig. 1) which have condition for S—S bond fission apparently analogous to that of

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

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